

Chemistry of Cerium (III). Part I. An Electrometric Study on the Quantitative Precipitation of Cerium (III) as Normal Selenite

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The results of a series of conductometric titrations of cerium (III) against selenous acid with an overall concentration of 70% ethanol have been reported; the possibility of carrying out direct as well as reverse titrations over a wide concentration range of cerium(III) is thereby concluded and the effect of ethanol concentration has also been studied which under cited conditions lends support to the formation of cerous normal selenite [molar ratio of Ce (III): Se being 2:3].

Berzelius, Nilson, Jannek, Moyer, Muspratt, Boutzourcano, and others¹ have studied the preparation and properties of selenites of alkali, alkaline earth and rare earth metals along with those of Cu, Ag, Zn, Cd, Hg, Al, In, Tl, TiO^{2+} , ZrO^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , Th, Pb, Sn, Sb, Bi, Co, Ni, Fe, and Mn in detail.

Jolin and Swon² observed that addition of selenous acid to a concentrated cerous salt solution did not yield precipitate of cerous selenite till ammonia was added.

Dashmukh *et al.* used SO_3^{2-} in amperometric determination³⁻⁵ of Pb, Cu, Cd, and Co and conductometric determination of thorium⁶. They also estimated cobalt⁷ gravimetrically as normal selenite.

Keeping the applicability of SO_3^{2-} in view in analytical chemistry, the work has been extended to conductometric titrations of cerium(III) with selenous acid under different experimental conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Selenous acid was prepared by dissolving Morek's sample in conductivity water and selenium was estimated as Se by the usual gravimetric method⁸. Cerous nitrate (Merck's pure) was dissolved in conductivity water and Ce in the solution was estimated by the iodate method⁹.

1. Mellor, "A Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", 1930, Vol. X, p. 620.

2. *Akad. Handl. Bih.*, 1874, 2, No. 14, 69.

3. *J. Sci. Res., B.H. Univ.*, 1959, 10, 41.

4. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 229.

5. *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1961, 182, 324.

6. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 356.

7. *Ibid.*, 1960, 19B, 103.

8. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 1955, p. 442.

9. Vogel, *ibid.*, p. 473.

The respective molar concentrations of the two solutions were $0.1314 M$ and $0.1315 M$. Different volumes of $0.1315 M$ $Ce(NO_3)_3$ solution were made to 65 ml and direct conductometric titrations carried out at $0.0004045 M$, $0.000809 M$, $0.001011 M$, $0.001213 M$, $0.001416 M$, $0.001618 M$, $0.00182 M$, and $0.002022 M$ concentrations of cerium (III) against $0.1314 M$ H_2SeO_3 solution. In reverse titrations, different volumes of $0.1314 M$ H_2SeO_3 were made to 65 ml and these solutions at $0.001213 M$, $0.001516 M$, $0.001819 M$, $0.002122 M$, and $0.002426 M$ concentrations titrated against $0.1315 M$ $Ce(NO_3)_3$. In studying the effect of ethanol, 65 ml of $0.002022 M$ $Ce(NO_3)_3$ solution containing 0, 40, 50, 60, 70, and 80% ethanol was titrated against $0.1314 M$ H_2SeO_3 .

FIG. 1. Direct conductometric titration.

Mullard conductivity bridge, type E7566, a 220-volt, A. C. line operated, direct-reading electronic instrument with an electron beam indicator for the balance were used for the conductance measurements. The readings were recorded in mhos at 50 cycles. The conductometric titration dip-cell of the type E7591 with platinised bright platinum electrodes and 10-ml microburette was connected to the terminal cell on the meter; the main switch was turned on and the selector switch to "mhos" for recording the conductance directly.

The instrument was set to the zero-loss angle for highest sensitivity. The range switch was switched to the expected range and the pointer knob rotated till the electron beam indicator showed the maximum shadow angle. The scale value was recorded and multiplied by the factor indicated on the range-selector switch to find the conductance directly.

FIG. 2. Direct conductometric titration.

Direct Conductometric Titrations.—A known volume of cerous nitrate solution with an overall 70% of ethanol was taken in the cell, placed on a magnetic stirrer, the dip cell was properly dipped in solution, and the initial conductance recorded. Selenous acid solution was added from a microburette in small amounts to the cerous nitrate solution, the mixture stirred well, and the reading recorded after allowing the precipitate to settle. The temperature was maintained at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$ by circulating a current of water from a constant temperature water bath in a jacket provided with the reaction vessel (cell) for the purpose. The conductances were plotted against the volumes of the titrant (Figs. 1 and 2).

Reverse Conductometric Titrations.—In the titration of selenous acid against cerous nitrate solution, a known volume of selenous acid containing 70% by volume of ethanol was taken in the cell and cerous nitrate solution was added from the microburette, other procedure being the same as given above. The results are plotted in Figs. 3 and 4 (Curves I—V).

FIG. 3. Reverse conductometric titration.

Effect of Ethanol at Different Concentrations.—Addition of selenous acid to cerous nitrate solution could not bring about the precipitation of cerium in the form of its normal selenite in aqueous medium, but a change was recorded in the conductance much before the end point, which indicated the formation of selenite, though the curve

was neither smooth nor the break was sharp, leading to no well-defined end-point and so the addition of ethanol seemed to be a necessity. Experiments were therefore carried out at various ethanolic concentrations in which 70% ethanolic concentration afforded the correct end point. The results obtained are shown in Fig. 5 (Curves I—VI).

FIG. 4. Reverse conductometric titration.

DISCUSSION

The reaction involved in the present titration may be represented as

Discrepancies arising in the smoothness of the curve, sharpness of the break, and premature end point in purely aqueous medium may be attributed to the dissolution of the precipitate and its hydrolysis under cited condition which could be checked by addition of the requisite amount of ethanol (70%) to provide a correct end point.

Breaks recorded in direct and reverse titrations correspond to the molar ratio of 2:3 for cerium and selenium, showing thereby the formation of normal cerium selenite, the only possibility under cited conditions.

FIG. 5 Effect of EtOH on conductometric titration.

Thus this method is an accurate and easy titrimetric procedure for the determination of trivalent cerium on micro scale.

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